

OCEAN:ICE News – June 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to June's OCEAN:ICE News! We're thrilled to keep you updated on the latest from the world of OCEAN:ICE.

Read on to get to know our featured researcher of the month, learn about OCEAN:ICE becoming an early adopter of the EU Open Research Repository pilot, and catch up on the latest OCEAN:ICE activities, including our Data Management Workshop, IMDIS 2024, and Digital Ocean Forum 2024. Moreover, mark your calendars for the upcoming OCEAN:ICE Work Package 3 Webinar and FRISP 2024 meeting, stay informed about the upcoming Climate Coffees and where you can find OCEAN:ICE in action at various events.

Enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to bringing you more news in July!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Mathias C. van Caspel

We are continuing with our article series 'Researcher in the Spotlight'. Check out our latest feature on Mathias C. van Caspel, a post-doctoral researcher in ocean modelling with a circumpolar focus, at [AWI](#).

Read the feature on Mathias [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

OCEAN:ICE - Early Adopter of the EU Open Research Repository Pilot

OCEAN:ICE is very proud to be an early adopter of the EU Open Research Repository Pilot. The status of early adopter will allow OCEAN:ICE to share more broadly its results via an enhanced version of Zenodo by setting up a trusted repository within Zenodo. The mission of the repository is to support the implementation of the EU's open science policy, providing a trusted and comprehensive space for researchers to share their research outputs such as data, software, reports, presentations, posters and more. The EU Open Research Repository simplifies the process of complying with open science requirements, ensuring that research outputs from Horizon Europe are freely accessible, thereby accelerating scientific discovery and innovation.

Go to our [website](#) to learn more about the project, the advantages of becoming an early adopter and the repository.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

OCEAN:ICE Data Management Workshop 2024

OCEAN:ICE Data Management Workshop, held online on the 22nd of May 2024, was a key event for advancing data management practices within the OCEAN:ICE project.

Central to the workshop was the introduction and discussion of the [Data Management Plan](#) (DMP), which is mandatory under Horizon Europe and underpins the Open Science framework. The DMP is a living document, evolving over the course of the project, detailing how data is collected, processed, and shared. It ensures the availability and utility of research data, setting guidelines for data deposit and emphasising the importance of using trusted repositories such as NODCs, SEANOE, and PANGAEA, and more. Participants were reminded of the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary," encouraging the open sharing of data by default while protecting sensitive information.

The workshop also covered metadata standards and recommendations, which are crucial for ensuring that data is discoverable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR principles). Participants were guided on how to provide comprehensive metadata, including details on data collection methods, locations, timestamps, and processing techniques. Emphasis was placed on using standard metadata formats and licenses, preferably CC-BY or CC0, to facilitate open access and proper attribution of data sources.

The [OCEAN:ICE data infrastructure](#) was another major topic. The infrastructure comprises several layers, including the application, service, and data layers, which work together to support data management and dissemination. Tools such as ERDDAP(TM), GeoServer, and GeoNetwork were highlighted for their roles in data publishing, metadata harmonization, and providing user-friendly interfaces for data access. The infrastructure aims to support near real-time and delayed mode data management, ensuring that data is quickly available for immediate use and archived for long-term access.

Learn more about the OCEAN:ICE Data Management Workshop 2024 on our [website](#).

International Conference on Marine Data and Information Systems (IMDIS) 2024

From May 27th to 29th, 2024, in Bergen, Norway, the OCEAN:ICE project partner, [ETT](#), participated in [IMDIS 2024, the International Conference on Marine Data and Information Systems](#). This conference, held every three years, brings together experts in information technology, marine data management, research, environmental protection, and more. The event provided updates on ocean data standards, products, services, and the activities of marine infrastructures and observational systems.

ETT's R&D Manager in SmartCity & Sustainability, Antonio Novellino, presented three posters, including one on observations of the Southern Ocean titled 'Information Systems and Tools to Support Antarctic Communities', in the session 'Technical Developments for Marine Information and Data Management.' The presentation highlighted significant advancements in data management and the development of tools designed to support the Antarctic research community.

The poster, titled 'Information Systems and Tools to Support Antarctic Communities', showcased the collaborative efforts of multiple international projects and organizations, including [SOOS](#), [SO-CHIC](#), [EMODnet](#), and [OCEAN:ICE](#). Together, they emphasised the importance of integrated and multidisciplinary observations of the Southern Ocean to understand its state, variability, and broader climatic impacts.

Read more highlights from IMDIS 2024 on our [website](#).

Digital Ocean Forum (DOF) 2024

The OCEAN:ICE project was represented by the UK Grant Coordinator and Principal Investigator, Andrew Meijers (UKRI-BAS), at the 3rd Digital Ocean Forum (DOF2024), on 12-13 June 2024 in Brussels.

The Digital Ocean Forum 2024 (DOF2024) is an official event under the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the European Union. DOF2024 is organised by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research (DG RTD), Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE), Mercator Ocean International and VLIZ.

The OCEAN:ICE participated in the Scientific and Technical Workshop on the 12th of June in Brussels as a contributor to the [European Digital Twin of the Ocean \(European DTO\)](#).

The European Digital Twin Ocean and Digital Ocean Forum foster innovation through co-creation and collaboration, community assets, science, and technology to build a thriving digital ecosystem.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

OCEAN:ICE at the Forum for Research of Ice Shelf Processes (FRISP) 2024

The Forum for Research of Ice Shelf Processes (FRISP) is a forum for science around ice sheets, ice shelves and oceans around Antarctica and Greenland. This year, the 37th FRISP-meeting will be held on 19-21 June 2024 at the [Klimahaus](#) in Bremerhaven, Germany, organised by OCEAN:ICE members [Markus Janout](#), [Mathias C. van Caspel](#) and [Ralph Timmermann](#) from the [Alfred-Wegener-Institute](#).

Around 70 international participants will gather to discuss their research, fieldwork and project plans with talks and poster presentations, and to foster collaborations and exchange ideas during coffee breaks and dinner activities.

A link to the FRISP 2024 agenda can be found [here](#).

A promotional poster for the OCEAN:ICE event at FRISP 2024. The background is a photograph of a large ice shelf over the ocean. The OCEAN:ICE logo is in the top left. The main title 'OCEAN:ICE at FRISP' is in large white letters across the middle. Below it, the dates '19 - 21 June 2024 | Bremerhaven' are written. At the bottom left is the European Union flag, and to its right is text about funding from the European Union and UK Research and Innovation.

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OCEAN:ICE at FRISP

19 - 21 June 2024 | Bremerhaven

OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

OCEAN:ICE Work Package 3 Webinar

The [OCEAN:ICE](#) project assess the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes on Planet Earth, via their influence on sea level rise, deep water formation, ocean circulation and climate.

[Work Package 3](#) (WP3) focuses on providing updated values and uncertainties for freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic Ice Sheet to the ocean over the satellite observational period to the present day, including surface melt and runoff, ice flow, basal melt, and calving. WP3 assess uncertainty in the updated freshwater fluxes and will deliver improved dynamical ice sheet model process representation.

OCEAN:ICE WP3 Webinar '*Ice Sheet Mass Balance, Forcing and Dynamics*' will feature talks by Work Package 3 Leader, Dr Ruth Mottram, and senior scientists, followed by a public Q&A session.

The OCEAN:ICE webinar series is hosted and coordinated by the [European Polar Board](#), in conjunction with the OCEAN:ICE Project Coordinator and WP Leads.

A recording of the webinar will be publicly available afterwards on the [OCEAN:ICE YouTube channel](#).

Register [here](#) for the webinar.

OCEAN:ICE **EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD**

OCEAN:ICE WP3 WEBINAR

ICE SHEET MASS BALANCE, FORCING AND DYNAMICS

This webinar will be the second in a series introducing the EU-funded OCEAN:ICE project.

**27 June 2024
14:00 CEST**

© Dr Renuka Badhe

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Climate Coffee

[Oliver Huhn](#) on *Record of water mass age and meltwater fractions, Weddell Sea*
1 August 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CET).

Climate Coffee

Oliver Huhn, University of Bremen

**Record of water mass age and meltwater fractions,
Weddell Sea**

1 August 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 19-21 June 2024, [FRISP 2024](#), Bremerhaven
- 4-9 August 2024, [International Symposium on Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models](#), Newcastle
- 19-23 August 2024, [11th SCAR Open Science Conference](#), Pucón & online
- 21-23 August 2024, [Nordic Meteorologist Meeting](#), Copenhagen

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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www.ocean-ice.eu

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<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

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Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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